

SECTION III
ETHNOCULTURAL STUDIES AND THEIR LINGUISTIC MANIFESTATIONS:
LINGUISTIC AND LINGUODIDACTIC ASPECTS

GENDER ASPECT IN PHRASEOLOGY

*N. Nasrullaeva*¹

Abstract:

The present article is devoted to the analysis of genderly marked phraseological units of the English and Uzbek languages. The author defines four types of gender semantics, explains them and gives examples to each of these types. There is a deep analysis of gender semantics in the structure of phraseological units.

Key words: gender semantics, phraseological unit, gender component, masculine, feminine

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Being an important aspect of modern linguistics, phraseology exists almost in all language spheres: in discourse analysis, speech communication and business sphere. Phraseology is one of the most significant fragments of lingual worldview. Phraseology demonstrates a great store of knowledge about culture, religion, history, literature, geography, etc. Besides, phraseological units disclose information that deals with gender peculiarities of society development. That's why investigation of phraseological units in the aspect of gender linguistics becomes very actual and important.

Gender investigation of phraseological units (further PhU) is actual as in the centre of its attention there are cultural and social factors determining social attitude to men and women and peculiarities of using linguistics means due to belonging to a definite sex. Actual becomes also a deep investigation of the process of gender conceptualization, characterization of its layers and containing parts, finding out factors and parameters forming basic gender concepts taking into account their national-cultural, etymological and historical peculiarities.

In the aspect of gender linguistics all the phraseological units are divided into two main types: genderly marked and genderly neutral. We are interested in genderly marked phraseological units, i.e. phraseological units which contain gender component (noun, pronoun, proper name) with direct indicator at a definite sex, for example: *nurse, soldier, he, her, Alice, Tom*, etc.

The basis of investigation of phraseological meaning became the conception of idioms semantics proposed by V.N. Teliya as the hierarchal model expressed in the

¹ *Nasrullaeva Nafisa Zafarovna, Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

shape of macro components forming the semantic structure of idioms: 1) descriptive macro component or the content expressed in the meaning of phraseological units; 2) evaluative macro component denoting idiom's value; 3) motivating macro component denoting image suiting the reality or not suiting and belonging to its imagination; 4) emotive macro component uniting information about emotive content of phraseological units; 5) stylistic macro component; 6) grammatical macro component or information about morphological, syntactical and phonetic forms of idioms [V.N. Teliya, 1996, p. 34].

I.V. Zikova proposes hypotheses of existence of one more component – gender macro component in the semantics of phraseologisms which interact with all pointed above. This macro component which covers idiom's description helps to reflect cultural notions masculine / feminine in adequate way [I.V. Zikova, 2002, p.29].

In the process of investigation there were found the following semantic groups, expressing subjective-objective marks:

1) Phraseological units with component of femininity, characterizing a woman from negative side, contemptuously, disapprovingly, except phraseological units relating to mother, sister, woman-heroine: *light-minded woman* – negatively; *Sister Ann* – a faithful friend – positively.

2) Phraseological units with component of masculinity, characterizing a man by various marks, but mostly dominate positive and neutral marks: *a hen-pecked husband* – a man who is managed by his wife – negatively; *a man of letters* – a man-writer – neutrally; *square John* – an honest, decent man – positively; *a man of his word* – a man who keeps his promise – positively.

3) Phraseological units with component of femininity for characterizing a man, mostly negatively marked: *old woman* – a shy, coward man – negatively; *a girl's blouse* – a scandalous man – negatively.

4) Phraseological units with component of masculinity for characterizing a woman, mostly negatively marked: *a tom-boy* – hyperactive girl behaving like a boy – negatively; *man-eater* – a woman who uses men only for sexual relations – negatively.

5) Phraseological units with component of femininity relating to both genders, mostly dominates negative mark: *mother's darling* – mother's beloved son or daughter – negative; *a weak sister* – an unreliable person – negative [N.Z.Nasrullaeva, 2018, p.89].

As the result of the analysis of gender meaning formation in genderly marked phraseological units of the English and Uzbek languages, there were proposed four main types of gender semantics:

Directive gender semantics – (from the English word «direct») directly points at masculinity or femininity and contains gender component with explicit (open) way of gender meaning actualization, for example:

Uzbek phraseological units: Ashir tarnov – a very tall, awkward man (Ashir is a man's name); hotin boshi bilan – being a woman, in spite of belonging to a weaker sex (hotin is an Uzbek word which means “a woman”); kelin ko'rmoq – 1) to visit a new bride; 2) to bring a new bride to one's house, to have a bride in one's house (kelin is an Uzbek word which means “a bride”); bo'z yigit – a young fellow, a young man.

English phraseological units: lord of creation – a man, male; maid of honour – queen's servant (female), bride's friend (female); between men and men – (to speak) as a man with a man; Tom (Jack) o'Bedlam – a mad man.

Oppositive gender semantics – (from the English word «opposite») contains genderly marked component, which indicates at a definite sex but characterizes a representative of the opposite sex, for example:

Uzbek phraseological units: hotinboz – a man who likes to have close relations with ladies (hotin is an Uzbek word which means “a woman”); erkakshoda – a rude woman, who looks like a man (erkak is an Uzbek word which means “a man”); Miss Molly (Nancy) – a tender man or a fellow who looks like a girl (Miss is used for a single girl); Lizzie boy – a tender man (Lizzie is a girl's name); girl boy – a boy who by his behavior and manner looks like a girl; bachelor girl – a single self-supporting independent girl (bachelor is used for a single man).

As it is obvious in the examples, such “feminine” words as “hotin”, “Miss”, “Lizzie” and “girl” are used for characterization of representatives of male sex, but “masculine” words such as “erkak” and “bachelor” are used for female representatives.

Transformative gender semantics – (from the English word «transformative») contains gender component with implicit (concealed) gender component and actualizes its gender meaning by metaphorical transformation: mo'yl abi ham g'am emaydi – he is indifferent (mo'ylab is an Uzbek word which means “beard”); ketini mo'yc hinak tishlamagan – he has never suffered from misery, poverty and problems (mo'ychinak is an Uzbek word which means “moustache picker”); mosh-guruch – 2) belonging to different sexes (mosh is an Uzbek word which means “beans”, guruch is an Uzbek word which means “rice”); breeches part – man's role in theatre; beauty and the beast – a beautiful lady and an ugly man. In these examples it's difficult to make out gender components as from the semantics point of view, they are not direct indicators of a definite sex.

Disaparative gender semantics – (from the English word «disappear») contains gender component which doesn't actualizes its gender meaning and characterizes another (free from gender indexing) thing, event or phenomenon. There were found many English phraseological units which don't actualize their gender meaning, for example:

English examples with disparative gender semantics: long Eliza – blue and white Chinese vase with women's images (Eliza – a girl's name); long Tom – a kind of fire-gun (Tom – a boy's name); maiden trip (или voyage) – first trip, first voyage (of a new ship) (maiden – a single girl); a snow man – a figure made of snow; iron man – dollar; the lower men – legs (in the last examples a word “man” is used).

Disaparative gender semantics can also be formed by verbs: jump a man – to get a dice in game; the inner man – stomach. These expressions do not characterize men or women though they have genderly marked component in their structure. Gender meaning in such phraseological units disappear in the process of general meaning of phraseological units.

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